

MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMAL DG PLACEMENT AND SIZING IN DISTRIBUTION SYSTEMS USING LSF-MALO: A STUDY ON VARIOUS DG CONFIGURATIONS AND LOAD

NUR ATIQAH ABDUL RAHMAN¹, ZULKIFFLI ABDUL HAMID², NUR ASHIDA SALIM³, ISMAIL MUSIRIN⁴

¹ Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Sarawak, 94300, Kota Samarahan, Sarawak, Malaysia

^{2,4}Power System Operations Computational Intelligence (POSC) Research Group, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia

³Power System Planning and Operations (PoSPO) Research Group, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia

E-mail: ¹nur_atiqah019@uitm.edu.my, ²zulkiffli9947@uitm.edu.my, ³nurashida606@uitm.edu.my, ⁴ismailbm@uitm.edu.my

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the optimization of Distributed Generation (DG) placement and sizing in power distribution systems using the Loss Sensitivity Factor-Mutated Ant Lion Optimizer (LSF-MALO) algorithm. The goal is to minimize real power losses, enhance voltage stability, and reduce economic losses by strategically deploying DG units, such as photovoltaic (PV), diesel, and wind turbines, in distribution networks. The LSF-MALO algorithm's effectiveness is evaluated using the IEEE 69-bus system, under varying load scenarios and DG configurations. The results are compared with other optimization methods (LSF-Analytical, EP, and MALO), showing that LSF-MALO consistently outperforms them, particularly in multi-type DG configurations like PV-Diesel-Wind and PV-PV-Wind. The findings demonstrate that LSF-MALO not only achieves significant reductions in power losses and improvements in voltage profiles but also provides substantial cost savings, highlighting its potential for improving the efficiency and sustainability of modern power distribution systems. The study underscores the importance of LSF-MALO as a robust tool for optimizing DG integration in the context of decentralized, eco-friendly energy systems.

Keywords: *Distributed Generation (DG), Loss Sensitivity Factor-Mutated Ant Lion Optimizer (LSF-MALO), Distribution Network, Multi-Objective, Voltage Stability, Optimization Technique*

1. INTRODUCTION

The global shift from traditional centralized power generation to localized, decentralized energy sources is driven by the depletion of fossil fuels, the environmental impact of conventional energy, and the growing inefficiencies in transmission and distribution networks. Centralized power generation frequently involves substantial costs, considerable transmission losses, and environmental challenges [1]. Distributed Generation (DG) has emerged as a critical solution in modern power systems, offering a decentralized approach to energy production. Unlike traditional power plants, DG units are strategically placed throughout the distribution network, providing localized energy solutions that enhance system reliability, flexibility, and efficiency. While DG offers several advantages over centralized generations, such as reducing transmission losses and supporting environmental

sustainability, its successful integration into the power grid requires careful optimization of placement and sizing. This paper proposes a novel optimization approach using the Loss Sensitivity Factor-Mutated Ant Lion Optimizer (LSF-MALO) algorithm to address the multi-objective challenges in DG placement, minimizing real power losses, improving voltage stability, and reducing operational costs. This research highlights the importance of meticulous planning to ensure that DG deployment does not compromise system stability or performance.

DG refers to energy sources that are directly connected to the distribution network, providing and maintaining power for local customers [2]. These sources are strategically integrated into the distribution system to enhance local supply and reliability. Typically, DG units vary in size, generally ranging from 50 MW to 300 MW [3]. This scale allows for a more manageable and

flexible integration compared to large, centralized power plants, enabling better adaptation to local energy demands and supporting the overall efficiency and stability of the power grid.

There are two main types of DG: non-renewable and renewable sources. Non-renewable distributed generation sources consist of technologies like diesel generators, micro turbines, and fuel cells. These sources provide localized power generation, offering stable energy solutions that are necessary for assisting the distribution network. On the other hand, renewable DG sources encompass sustainable technologies such as photovoltaic (PV) systems, wind turbines, hydroelectric plants, geothermal energy systems, tidal energy converters, and bio-fuel systems [4]. Renewable sources use available natural resources to generate power, working as an important component in promoting environmental sustainability and reducing the reliance on fossil fuels. By extending the types of distributed generation (DG) used, the energy industry can establish a power distribution network that is more robust, efficient, and environmentally friendly.

The adoption of distributed generation (DG) presents key benefits over conventional power systems, such as voltage profile enhancement, greater stability, congestion mitigation in transmission and distribution networks, lower pollutant emissions, and decreased power wastage [5]. From a technological perspective, the advancement of small-scale development can be further enhanced [6]. Furthermore, the integration of DG offers significant advantages such as minimizing real power losses, improving voltage profile, enhancing system reliability, and enhancing power quality [7]. During unexpected circumstances, such as abrupt power failures caused by line outages, DG can serve as an alternative power source.

While the integration of DG offers significant benefits, it also presents challenges such as compromised system stability and power quality if not properly planned or excessively deployed. Nevertheless, these advantages can only be fully realized through optimal DG sizing and strategic placement within the network [8], [9]. It may also lead to voltage flickering, excessive voltages, excessive power losses, increased short circuit current [7], and a risk of out-of-phase reclosure that can cause damage to the surrounding loads and feeders of the distribution system [10]. Therefore, researchers are currently interested in determining the optimal location for integrating DG into the grid. This involves finding suitable capacity and

quantity of DG installations that will not compromise the stability of the system.

Numerous studies have employed metaheuristic algorithms to optimize DG placement and sizing, addressing the challenges of nonlinear power flow dynamics and system constraints. For instance, Adnan et al. (2024) introduced the Sand Cat Swarm Optimization (SCSO) algorithm, which demonstrated superior performance in loss minimization (40.77% reduction) compared to conventional methods like Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) when applied to the IEEE 14-bus system. However, a key limitation across these studies is their narrow focus on loss minimization, neglecting other critical power system parameters, which restricts their practical applicability for large-scale, real-time implementations [11].

Many studies have been carried out on the optimal placement of distributed generation to tackle multi-objective problems effectively. The research [12] presents a new technique called Multi-Objective Integrated Immune Moth Flame Evolutionary Programming (MO-IIMFEP) for efficiently determining the optimal placement of type 3 DG in a distribution system. The objective is to minimize the total active power losses, cumulative voltage deviation, and total operating cost. The method effectively reduces power losses, improves voltage stability, and lowers operational costs in the distribution network. Although MO-IIMFEP demonstrates satisfactory performance on the studied system, additional assessment of various types of DG is required to determine its overall suitability. It is crucial to consider that the algorithm's efficacy may differ depending on the type of DG and the loading scenarios.

The study presented in [13] proposes applying Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) for optimal placement and sizing of DG in distribution networks. The objective is to minimize the total apparent power losses, the voltage deviation index, the DG installation costs, and the pollutant emissions. This study enables the assessment of diverse DG technologies, offering valuable insights into the compromises and advantages of alternative solutions. This information is essential for system planners and operators when choosing the most appropriate technology for specific situations. Although the study has shown substantial improvements in reducing power loss and enhancing the voltage profile, it only focuses on the base case system and does not consider other system conditions.

The author in [14] utilizes a Multi-Objective Whale Optimization Algorithm (MOWOA) to

address the issue of DG placement and sizing. The objective is to reduce power losses and annual economic losses while simultaneously enhancing voltage profiles and system reliability. The results demonstrate reduced active power losses and annual economic losses, demonstrating their efficiency in comparison to other algorithms. Nevertheless, the study's scope is restricted to a single type of DG and a typical scenario of the test systems. The efficacy of the suggested method may fluctuate based on the network's characteristics and the types of distributed generation (DG) units utilized.

The research in [15] employs a hybrid optimization technique called BPSO-SLFA, which combines Binary Particle Swarm Optimization (BPSO) and Shuffled Leap Frog technique (SLFA). The objective of this algorithm is to determine the best locations and sizes for Distributed Generators (DG) for minimizing power loss and maximizing voltage stability. The implementation of the BPSO-SLFA algorithm led to substantial decreases in power losses and enhancements in voltage profiles. Although it offers excellent performance in reducing power losses, significant improvements in voltage profiles, and the capability to handle multiple DG placements simultaneously, the study mainly focuses on technical optimization without extensively considering other factors such as cost and environmental impact. The study was restricted to one type of distributed generation (DG) and standard systems.

The paper presented [16] presents a new algorithm called Multi-Objective Opposition-Based Chaotic Differential Evolution (MOCDE). The study is centered on minimizing the impact of the following three main objectives: power loss, annual economic loss associated with DG, and voltage deviation. The aim is to optimize system efficiency by decreasing overall costs, enhancing voltage profiles, and reducing power loss. The study demonstrated the efficacy of the proposed approach in harmonizing conflicting aims by offering a range of ideal options. Furthermore, the MOCDE method successfully prevents premature convergence and ensures a resilient solution set by maintaining diversity within the population. Nevertheless, the efficiency of the algorithm can be influenced by the choice of control parameters, such as the mutation factor and crossover rate. Incorrect parameter configurations might result in insignificant solutions or early convergence. The scope is restricted to the standard system and only one type of DG.

The significance of multi-objective functions in the integration of DG into distribution systems

cannot be overstated. This paper aims to establish the optimal placement and size of DG in the distribution system to address multiple objectives. These objectives include minimizing power losses, improving voltage magnitude, and reducing overall costs. The proposed algorithm for this optimization problem is called Loss Sensitivity Factor – Mutated Ant Lion Optimizer (LSF-MALO). This approach promises that the installation of DG not only enhances the performance of the system but also aligns with wider goals such as economic efficiency and environmental sustainability. By taking these measures, decision-makers can make well-informed decisions that effectively balance conflicting priorities, thereby promoting the shift towards a more robust, efficient, and sustainable power infrastructure. The LSF-MALO algorithm has been applied to optimize the placement and sizing of Distributed Generation (DG) in the IEEE 69 bus system.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Problem Formulation

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of the LSF-MALO algorithm [17] when dealing with multi-objective problems. The parameters evaluated were to minimize real power losses, increase voltage magnitude, and minimize cost. The real power losses will be assessed using load flow simulation. The power loss in an N-bus distribution system can be mathematically represented by the equation (1) [14].

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N [\alpha_{ij}(P_i P_j + Q_i Q_j) + \beta_{ij}(Q_i P_j + P_i Q_j)] \quad (1)$$

where Z_{ij} is the impedance of the line between bus i and bus j ; r_{ij} is the line resistance between bus i and bus j ; x_{ij} is the line reactance between bus i and bus j ; V_i is the voltage magnitude at bus i ; V_j is the voltage magnitude at bus j ; δ_i is the voltage angle at bus i ; δ_j is the voltage angle at bus j ; P_i and Q_i is the active and reactive power injections at bus i and P_j and Q_j is the active and reactive power injections at bus j . The calculation of real power losses in load flow simulation is subjected to the following equality and non-equality constraints as follows:

$$P_{Gi} - P_{Di} = \sum_{j=1}^N V_i V_j [G_{ij} \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j) + B_{ij} \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j)];$$

... $\forall i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ (2)

$$Q_{Gi} - Q_{Di} = \sum_{j=1}^N V_i V_j [G_{ij} \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j) + B_{ij} \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j)];$$

$$\dots \forall i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

$$P_{Gi}^{min} \leq P_{Gi} \leq P_{Gi}^{max} \quad (4)$$

$$Q_{Gi}^{min} \leq Q_{Gi} \leq Q_{Gi}^{max} \quad (5)$$

$$V_i^{min} \leq V_i \leq V_i^{max} \quad (6)$$

where, G_{ij} is the conductance of the line between bus i and bus j and B_{ij} is the susceptance of the line between bus i and bus j . P_{Gi} and Q_{Gi} are the power generations of generators at bus i . P_{Di} and Q_{Di} are the loads at bus i and V_i is the bus voltage magnitude.

Furthermore, this study incorporated an evaluation of annual costs by comparing two scenarios: one that incorporated the installation of DG and another that did not. The economic impact can be assessed by calculating the annual economic losses for each scenario. The economic benefits of efficiently integrating distributed generation (DG) into the distribution system can be evaluated by considering the annual cost as one of the factors. This highlighted the possibility of reducing costs and improving performance. The annual economic loss (AEL) calculation was utilized to comprehensively analyze the economic implications associated with each scenario, as outlined below [14]:

$$AEL = (P_{loss} \times C_e \times 8760) + C_i \quad (7)$$

where P_{loss} is the real power losses in the system, C_e is the cost of energy loss per kWh in RM, 8760 is the total days in one year and C_i is the cost of installation of DG. The cost of installation of DG is considered zero without DG placement. The cost of installation, C_i is given as follows:

$$C_i = \frac{C_{DG} \times \sum_{i=1}^N P_{DG_i}}{L_{DG}} \quad (8)$$

where C_{DG} is the cost of DG per kW generated, including capital investment in DG as well as deployment, operation & maintenance costs, P_{DG_i} is the size of DG installed into the system and L_{DG} is the life span of DG. With an estimated 10-year lifespan [14] for the DG units, the planning horizon was set for a corresponding decade-long period. The cost of energy loss per kWh, C_e is RM 0.218 cent/kWh [19] and for cost of DG per kW generated, C_{DG} for PV, wind turbine and diesel engine distributed generator are RM 0.1901

cent/kWh [20], RM 0.9050 [21] cent/kWh and RM 1.54 cent/kWh [22] respectively.

The optimal placement of DG in a distribution system addresses these three parameters as multi-objective problems. The main objective is to reduce the real power losses, enhance the voltage magnitude, and minimize the annual cost. To maximise the voltage magnitude, a negative sign was utilised in defining this multi-objective problem, which indicates that the total equation is treated as a minimization problem. The weighted sum strategy was chosen to formulate this multi-objective problem. The multi-objective problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{minimize } f_{wsm} = W_1 P_{loss} - W_2 V_{min} + W_3 \text{cost} \quad (9)$$

where W_1, W_2 , and W_3 are the corresponding weights for real power losses, voltage magnitude and total annual economic loss. Each of these weights was determined via the R-Method, rather than through trial and error. This method was initially employed to prioritize the non-dominated solutions for Pareto-optimal solutions. The purpose of this R-method is to systematically allocate weights to objectives, allowing the evaluation of various solutions. It helps in selecting the ideal compromise solution from a collection of Pareto-optimal solutions in multi-objective optimization scenarios. In this study, the R-method was utilized to calculate the weight for the multi-objective function, as described in equation (9). The procedure to determine the weight of each objective is as follows:

1. Rank the objectives (V_{min} , P_{loss} , and Cost) according to their level of importance to determine their priority. If two or more goals are considered equally significant, give them an average rank.
2. The sum of all weights must be equal to one:

$$W_1 + W_2 + W_3 = 1 \quad (10)$$

3. The following equation is then used to determine the weight of the ranks.

$$W_j = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^j \left(\frac{1}{r_k} \right)} \right)}{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^j \left(\frac{1}{r_k} \right)} \right)} \quad (11)$$

where:

W_j = weight of objective j ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$)

r_k = rank of objective k ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, j$)

n = number of objectives

This problem is a multi-objective problem with three objectives; hence the value of n is equal to 3. The weights W_1 , W_2 and W_3 are determined as follow:

$$W_1 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1}}\right)}{\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1}} + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}}}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}+\frac{1}{3}}}\right)} = 0.4521$$

$$W_2 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}}}\right)}{\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1}} + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}}}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}+\frac{1}{3}}}\right)} = 0.3014$$

$$W_3 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}+\frac{1}{3}}}\right)}{\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1}} + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}}}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\frac{1}{2}+\frac{1}{3}}}\right)} = 0.2465$$

To obtain the annual economic saving (ACS), the AEL is performed before and after DG placement. The total annual economic saving is determined as follows:

$$ACS = AEL_{withDG} - AEL_{beforeDG} \quad (12)$$

where AEL_{withDG} is the annual economic loss with DG placement and $AEL_{beforeDG}$ is the annual economic loss before DG placement.

2.2 LSF-MALO Algorithm

The LSF-MALO algorithm, which combines the Loss Sensitivity Factor (LSF) with the Mutated Ant Lion Optimizer (MALO) hybrid algorithm, was introduced in reference [17]. The sensitivity factor will be determined for each bus in the system and used to establish a ranking, resulting in a priority list. The positioning of DGs is determined by a priority list, which aims to reduce the total computational time required for the optimization process. The sensitivity factor of real power losses with respect to DG real power injection has been defined as follows [23]:

$$\gamma_i = \frac{\partial P_L}{\partial P_i} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^N (\alpha_{ij} P_j - \beta_{ij} Q_j) \quad (13)$$

where, γ_i is the LSF index at the i -th bus, P_L is the total real power losses in the system, P_i is the net real power injection at the i -th bus, P_j and Q_j are the net real and reactive power injection at the j -th bus (i.e. those buses other than bus i), N is the number of buses in the system and α_{ij} and β_{ij} are the parameters calculated based on bus voltages and bus impedance matrix.

Prior to calculating the LSF indices, the test system undergoes a load flow analysis simulation to determine the necessary parameters for the computation. These parameters include bus voltages (both magnitude and angle), real power

losses, net real and reactive power injections at all buses, and the bus impedance matrix. Subsequently, the LSF indices are computed for each bus and organized in a decreasing order to create a priority list. The priority list will be utilized to generate a list of potential buses for DG locations before the sizing algorithm takes place.

The process proceeds by placing the Distributed Generation (DG) into the system and determining the most suitable size for the DG at the chosen position using the MALO algorithm, based on the bus's location acquired from the priority list. The MALO algorithm is a metaheuristic algorithm that combines the mutation operation from Evolutionary Programming (EP) with the Ant Lion Optimizer (ALO). The ALO concept is derived from the predatory behavior of antlions towards ants. The algorithms were developed by Seyedali Mirjalili in 2015 [24].

The population of ants and antlions serves as the ALO operators or search agents. The technique involves ants randomly exploring the search space, while assuming that the antlions are hiding somewhere within the same search space. The ants are presumed to have stochastic movement patterns in their natural search for food. The phenomenon of movement shown by ants is referred to as a random walk, where each ant in the group modifies its position according to this behavior. The random walk of an ant at t -th iteration is represented by equation (14):

$$X(t) = [0, \text{cumsum}(2r(t_1) - 1), \text{cumsum}(2r(t_2) - 1), \dots, \text{cumsum}(2r(t_n) - 1)] \quad (14)$$

where, cumsum computes the cumulative sum, n represents the maximum number of iterations, t denotes the random walk step or iteration, and $r(t)$ is a stochastic function defined as shown in equation (15):

$$r(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } rand > 0.5 \\ 0 & \text{if } rand \leq 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $rand$ is a random number generated with a uniform distribution in the range of $[0, 1]$.

Subsequently, the ants will modify their positions by random walks during each phase of optimization. However, because of the limitations of the search space, equation (14) cannot be directly used. Consequently, it is necessary to control the random walks to the search space throughout the optimization process. To ensure consistency, the random walk equation is normalized using equation (16):

$$X_i^t = \frac{(x_i^t - a_i) \times (d_i - c_i^t)}{(d_i^t - a_i)} + c_i \quad (16)$$

where a_i is the minimum random walk of the i -th variable, d_i is the maximum of the random walk in the i -th variable, c_i^t is the minimum of the i -th variable at the t -th iteration, and d_i^t indicates the maximum of the i -th variable at the t -th iteration. To ensure the existence of a random walk in the search space, equation (16) should be applied at each iteration [24]. The antlions' traps have an impact on the random walk of the ants. The effect is modelled using equations (17) and (18).

$$c_i^t = Antlion_j^t + c^t \quad (17)$$

$$d_i^t = Antlion_j^t + d^t \quad (18)$$

where, c^t is the minimum of all variables at the t -th iteration, d^t is the vector including the maximum of all variables at the t -th iteration, c_i^t is the minimum of all variables for the i -th ant, d_i^t is the maximum of all variables for the i -th ant and $Antlion_j^t$ indicates the position of the selected j -th antlion at the t -th iteration.

The antlion will be chosen as a representative to demonstrate its hunting capabilities. The antlion is chosen via roulette-wheel selection. Following this approach, antlions with better solutions are more likely to be selected for catching the ant. Therefore, the roulette-wheel antlion will be chosen for each ant in the population to ensure that it is able to capture the ant every time the ant moves randomly around it. Upon reaching the antlion's trap, the antlion hurls sand towards the centre of the pit, causing the ant to slide down and preventing its escape. The process was represented by equations (19) and (20):

$$c^t = \frac{c^t}{I} \quad (19)$$

$$d^t = \frac{d^t}{I} \quad (20)$$

where, I is a ratio, c^t is the minimum of all variables at the t -th iteration, and d^t is the vector including the maximum of all variables at the t -th iteration.

When an ant falls and reaches the bottom of the pit, the antlion captures and drags the ant into the sand prior to consuming it. In the ALO algorithm, this action is only applicable if the fitness of an ant is superior to that of the equivalent antlion. The antlion will coordinate its position with the most recent position of the ant it has captured. The

position of the antlion update is represented by equation (21):

$$Antlion_j^t = Ant_i^t ; \quad \text{if } f(Ant_i^t) > f(Antlion_j^t) \quad (21)$$

where, t is the current iteration, $Antlion_j^t$ is the position of the selected j -th antlion at the t -th iteration and Ant_i^t is the position of the i -th ant at the t -th iteration.

The elite antlion will serve as the optimal solution within the population, and it will be continuously updated at each iteration to guarantee the global optimum solution. Furthermore, the elite antlion possesses the capability to influence the movements of all ants during each iteration, in addition to the roulette-wheel antlion. Therefore, it is presumed that every ant in the population participates in a random walk around both the roulette-wheel antlion and the elite antlion at the same time. Consequently, the ant will shift its position by following a random walk around both antlions, outlined in equation (22):

$$Ant_i^t = \frac{R_A^t + R_E^t}{2} \quad (22)$$

where, R_A^t is the random walk around the antlion selected via the roulette wheel at the t -th iteration, R_E^t is the random walk around the elite antlion at t -th iteration and Ant_i^t is the updated position of the i -th ant at the t -th iteration.

In addition to elite and roulette-wheel antlions, the hybrid solution is generated by the introduction of an additional antlion known as the mutated antlion. The mutation technique from EP was selected due to its reproduction operator, which is more heuristic and straightforward when mapping the solution, and its superior convergence compared to the Genetic Algorithm (GA) [25]. The introduction of mutation can enhance the diversity of the population and mitigate the algorithm's propensity to become ensnared in local optima [24]. By introducing a new antlion, the random walk procedure for the ant's position will be influenced by other parameters. This will lead to reducing the exclusive reliance on the elite antlion and thus expanding the search area for the algorithm to explore. In addition, this approach allows for the acquisition of diverse solutions, so preventing the algorithm from getting trapped in local optima. Equation (20) will be updated upon the completion of the random walks conducted around the mutated antlion. The revised equation

for updating the ant location is denoted as equation (23):

$$Ant_i^t = \frac{R_A^t + R_E^t + R_M^t}{3} \quad (23)$$

where, Ant_i^t is the updated position of the i -th ant at the t -th iteration. The updated equation for ants' positions will introduce a range of solutions during each stage of optimization. This will decrease the algorithm's reliance on the elite antlion and help prevent local optima.

2.3 Incorporating Optimal DG Placement with LSF-MALO to Solve Multi-Objective Problem

Integrating DG units into the distribution system can bring numerous benefits, including improved system performance by reducing real power losses, increasing voltage magnitude, and lowering annual costs associated with DG losses and installation. However, the installation of DG must be carefully planned to maximize its benefits while maintaining system stability and reliability. The planning involves the best placement and sizing of the DG units.

The LSF-MALO algorithm has been implemented for the optimal placement and sizing of DG units using the following steps:

1. Load flow analysis: Prior to the installation of DG units, a load flow study will be conducted to determine the initial values of voltage magnitude and real power losses, serving as a baseline.
2. Loss Sensitivity Factor (LSF) calculation: LSF is calculated for each bus using equation (12). The buses are ranked in descending order based on the LSF value. The priority list will be constructed according to this ranking order, and only 40% of the list will be chosen to be included in the priority list. This list represents the possible selections for DG placement.
3. Initialization of MALO algorithm: The populations of ants and antlions were established. The initial positions of ants reflect possible configurations for DG placement, whereas antlions show potential optimal solutions. All algorithm parameters must be configured.
4. Ants' random walk and antlion traps: The ants followed a stochastic movement pattern within the search area throughout each iteration under the influence of antlion traps. Normalization must be applied to ensure that the random walk

remains within the boundaries of the system. Roulette wheel selection serves to choose antlions based on their fitness.

5. Mutation operation: Mutation operations have been implemented to guarantee the population's diversity. This will prevent the algorithm from becoming trapped in local optima. Antlions will have the opportunity to investigate new potential solutions during this phase.
6. Evaluation of fitness function: The evaluation of fitness following DG placement will be carried out at every iteration using equation (9). The antlions with the best fitness evaluation scores will be selected as elite antlions.
7. Convergence and optimal solution: Iterations will continue until the algorithm converges. This can be accomplished using either a specified threshold or a maximum number of iterations. The elite antlion with the best solution across the iterations is chosen as the optimal placement and sizing configuration for DG units.
8. Implementation and validation: The optimal placement and sizing of DG units determined by the LSF-MALO algorithm will be applied to the distribution system, and a final load flow analysis will be performed to validate the improvement in real power losses, magnitude voltage, and annual cost minimization.

The LSF-MALO algorithm incorporates DG units into the IEEE 69-bus distribution systems. The method underwent validation in various loading situations and with several types of DGs. The simulations were performed using MATLAB. Figure 1 represents the complete flowchart of optimal placement of DG with LSF-MALO to solve multi-objective problems.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study focuses on the multi-objective optimization problem of minimizing real power losses, enhancing voltage magnitude, while minimizing the annual economic loss in a power distribution network. The IEEE-69 Bus system has been utilized to implement the LSF-MALO technique for optimal placement of DG to address multi-objective challenges. When implementing DG technologies like PV, Diesel, and Wind

Turbine, it is crucial to carefully evaluate their

By using PV-PV-PV integration, the best

Figure 1: LSF-MALO Flow Chart for Multi Objective Problem

impact to meet these objectives, particularly when dealing with varying load situations. A comparative analysis was also carried out to compare this method with other methods, considering different increments of reactive load. The findings provide valuable insights into the efficacy of these techniques and their potential influence on power system optimization.

3.1 Optimal DG Placement with LSF-MALO to Solve Multi-Objective Problem

Table 1 tabulates the results after optimal DG placement in the IEEE 69-bus system, considering identical DG types. In this scenario, three DG units of the same category are integrated into the test system at specific load buses.

Based on Table 1, the proposed LSF-MALO technique consistently provides the best results in terms of reducing power losses (P_{loss}) and improving minimum voltage magnitudes (V_{min}) across different types of DG integrations.

performance results from the LSF-MALO technique with P_{loss} reduced to 0.105 MW, V_{min} improved to 0.978 p.u., and AEL reduced to RM199,538.00, which is equivalent to RM216,340.00 of ACS (52% of cost reduction). The next acceptable performance results from the MALO technique with P_{loss} of 0.204 MW, V_{min} of 0.957 p.u. and ACS of RM26,738.00, which is equivalent to 6.4% of cost saving. The LSF Analytical technique results in a negative cost saving of -100.7%, while the EP technique was unable to provide V_{min} above 0.95 p.u.

Next, the LSF-MALO technique with Diesel-Diesel integration is the most effective approach for the IEEE 69-bus system, providing the highest cost savings and substantial reduction in power losses and improvement in voltage magnitude. This type of DG integration shows superior performance in terms of ACS, with the LSF-MALO technique providing the highest cost saving percentage of 77.5% (equivalent to RM322,230.00), an improved V_{min} of 0.976 p.u. and a reduced P_{loss} of 0.049 MW as well. This is

followed by EP, MALO and LSF Analytical techniques with the cost saving percentages of 41.9%, 27.3% and -76.7% respectively.

The Wind-Wind-Wind integration shows a moderate performance for the LSF-MALO technique compared to the previous two DG integrations. However, this type of DG integration via LSF Analytical and MALO methods reflects an inefficient performance, leading to increased AEL, increased Ploss and negative cost savings as observed in Table 1.

On the other hand, Table 2 tabulates the results after optimal DG placement in the IEEE 69-bus system, considering combinational DG types. In this scenario, three DG units of different categories are integrated into the test system at specific load buses using the following combinations: PV-Diesel-Wind, PV-PV-Diesel and PV-PV-Wind.

Table 2 demonstrates that the optimal DG placement using combinational DG types significantly improves the voltage magnitude (V_{min}), power losses (P_{loss}), annual economic loss (AEL) and annual cost saving (ACS) as well. In this case, the LSF-MALO technique stands out as the most effective across different types of DG integrations, and it is followed by the EP technique. The different types of DG integrations by the LSF-MALO and EP techniques provide a balanced improvement in both technical and economic aspects.

Based on Table 2, the PV-Diesel-Wind integration via the proposed LSF-MALO technique provides the best improvement to the system; the V_{min} was improved to 0.973 p.u., P_{loss} was

significantly reduced to 0.099 MW and AEL was greatly reduced to RM190,042.00, resulting in 54.3% of ACS (equivalent to RM225,836.00). This is followed by the EP technique with ACS of 31.3%, however, at voltage magnitudes of below 0.95 p.u. The LSF Analytical and MALO techniques provide promising magnitudes of V_{min} ; however, their performance on Ploss and AEL is worse than that without the DG condition. The losses increase and ACS percentages are negative for these two methods.

The PV-PV-Diesel integration via LSF-MALO approach provides a comparable performance as that of its PV-Diesel-Wind integration, with an ACS percentage of 55.2%, an improved V_{min} of 0.973 p.u. and a reduced P_{loss} of 0.097 MW. Likewise, its PV-PV-Wind integration also results in almost comparable performance, with ACS percentage of 53.1%, V_{min} magnitude of 0.973 p.u. and P_{loss} value of 0.102 MW. Hence, for the IEEE 69-bus system, the LSF-MALO is the most effective technique for the integration of all DG types in the system.

The other methods reflect some inconsistencies in their results. As observed in Table 2, the LSF Analytical approach results in negative cost savings for all types of DG integrations. The EP technique suffers from undervoltage (V_{min} less than 0.95 p.u.) when PV-Diesel-Wind and PV-PV-Wind integrations were employed. In contrast, the MALO technique has a mixed performance for different types of DG integrations.

Table 1: Mitigation on voltage profiles, power losses and annual cost saving using optimal DG placement in IEEE 69-bus system - base case scenario with identical DG type

IDENTICAL DG TYPE									
Method	DG bus	DG Type	P_{DG} (MW)	Q_{DG} (MVar)	P_{loss} (MW)	V_{min} (p.u.)	AEL (RM)	ACS (RM)	%ACS
Without DG	-	-	-	-	0.218	0.910	415,878	-	-
LSF-MALO	61	PV	1.484	0.000	0.105	0.978	199,538	216,340	52.0
	62	PV	1.267	0.000					
	49	PV	0.837	0.000					
LSF Analytical	61	PV	1.837	0.000	0.437	0.991	834,470	-418,592	-100.7
	62	PV	1.837	0.000					
	64	PV	1.670	0.000					
EP	56	PV	2.393	0.000	0.152	0.941	289,641	126,237	30.4
	33	PV	0.677	0.000					
	10	PV	0.005	0.000					
MALO	56	PV	2.648	0.000	0.204	0.957	389,140	26,738	6.4
	33	PV	1.470	0.000					
	10	PV	2.256	0.000					
Without DG	-	-	-	-	0.218	0.910	415,878	-	-
LSF-MALO	61	Diesel	1.973	0.780	0.049	0.976	93,648	322,230	77.5

	62	Diesel	1.328	0.525					
	64	Diesel	2.260	0.893					
LSF Analytical	61	Diesel	1.837	0.726					
	62	Diesel	1.837	0.726	0.384	0.994	734,961	-319,083	-76.7
	64	Diesel	1.670	0.660					
EP	56	Diesel	2.474	0.978					
	33	Diesel	0.718	0.284	0.126	0.948	241,532	174,346	41.9
	10	Diesel	0.005	0.002					
MALO	56	Diesel	2.012	0.795					
	33	Diesel	1.367	0.540	0.158	0.958	302,256	113,622	27.3
	10	Diesel	2.299	0.909					
Without DG	-	-	-	-	0.218	0.910	415,878	-	-
LSF-MALO	61	Wind	2.160	-0.710					
	49	Wind	1.514	-0.498	0.200	0.972	382,749	33,129	8.0
	50	Wind	2.447	-0.804					
LSF Analytical	61	Wind	1.837	-0.604					
	62	Wind	1.837	-0.604	0.699	0.983	1,334,602	-918,724	-220.9
	64	Wind	1.670	-0.549					
EP	56	Wind	1.573	-0.517					
	33	Wind	0.005	-0.002	0.177	0.930	338,348	77,529	18.6
	10	Wind	0.589	-0.194					
MALO	56	Wind	3.540	-1.164					
	33	Wind	2.843	-0.935	0.407	0.957	778,067	-362,189	-87.1
	10	Wind	2.272	-0.747					

Table 2: Mitigation on voltage profiles, power losses and annual cost saving using optimal DG placement in IEEE 69-bus system - base case scenario with combinational DG type

COMBINATIONAL DG TYPE									
Method	DG bus	DG Type	P_{DG} (MW)	Q_{DG} (MVAr)	P_{loss} (MW)	V_{min} (p.u.)	AEL (RM)	ACS (RM)	%ACS
Without DG	-	-	-	-	0.218	0.910	415,878	-	-
LSF-MALO	61	PV	1.972	0.000					
	49	Diesel	1.327	0.524	0.099	0.973	190,042	225,836	54.3
	50	Wind	2.259	-0.743					
LSF Analytical	61	PV	1.837	0.000					
	62	Diesel	1.837	0.726	0.424	0.991	810,645	-394,767	-94.9
	64	Wind	1.670	-0.549					
EP	56	PV	2.298	0.000					
	33	Diesel	0.464	0.184	0.150	0.939	285,763	130,115	31.3
	10	Wind	0.005	-0.002					
MALO	56	PV	2.374	0.000					
	33	Diesel	2.382	0.941	0.253	0.950	483,250	-67,372	-16.2
	10	Wind	1.976	-0.649					
Without DG	-	-	-	-	0.218	0.910	415,878	-	-
LSF-MALO	61	PV	1.972	0.000					
	49	PV	1.327	0.000	0.097	0.973	186,389	229,488	55.2
	50	Diesel	2.259	0.893					
LSF Analytical	61	PV	1.837	0.000					
	62	PV	1.837	0.000	0.393	0.993	750,288	-334,410	-80.4
	64	Diesel	1.670	0.660					
EP	56	PV	2.303	0.000					
	33	PV	1.125	0.000	0.159	0.953	304,371	111,507	26.8
	10	Diesel	1.912	0.755					
MALO	56	PV	1.302	0.000					
	33	PV	0.622	0.000	0.140	0.940	266,839	149,039	35.8

	10	Diesel	1.691	0.668					
Without DG	-	-	-	-	0.218	0.910	415,878	-	-
LSF-MALO	61	PV	1.972	0.000					
	49	PV	1.327	0.000	0.102	0.973	195,198	220,680	53.1
	50	Wind	2.259	-0.743					
LSF Analytical	61	PV	1.837	0.000					
	62	PV	1.837	0.000	0.497	0.989	950,288	-534,410	-128.5
	64	Wind	1.670	-0.549					
EP	56	PV	2.426	0.000					
	33	PV	0.329	0.000	0.148	0.941	283,285	132,592	31.9
	10	Wind	0.005	-0.002					
MALO	56	PV	2.378	0.000					
	33	PV	2.380	0.000	0.245	0.950	467,379	-51,500	-12.4
	10	Wind	1.973	-0.648					

3.2 Comparison of optimal DG Implementation: Identical vs. Combinational DG Types

The effectiveness of DG implementation between identical and combinational DG types will be assessed in this section. The corresponding graphical illustrations, based on Table 1 and Table 2, on minimum voltage magnitude (V_{min}), annual economic loss (AEL), and annual cost saving (ACS) are presented in Figure 2 to Figure 4.

From Figure 2, the optimal DG placement by all methods results in an improved magnitude of V_{min} compared to the scenario without DG placement (dotted red line). However, the most effective technique is the LSF Analytical method, as the V_{min} magnitudes using any DG integration are at least 0.98 p.u. This is followed by the proposed LSF-MALO technique, which is also able to offer stable voltage magnitudes, with V_{min} well above 0.95 p.u (dotted green line) using any DG integrations. The MALO technique provides moderate performance on V_{min} with most of the DG integrations having a very slight improvement above 0.95 p.u. The EP technique, on the other hand, was unable to improve the voltage for most

of the DG integrations, except for the PV-PV-Diesel integration (purple bar), which shows a very slight improvement above 0.95 p.u.

From Figure 3, the optimal DG placement by most methods, except the LSF Analytical technique, also results in reduced AEL compared to the one without DG placement (dotted red line). Neglecting the Wind-Wind-Wind integration (yellow bar), the proposed LSF-MALO technique offers the lowest AEL of at most RM200,000.00 using the rest of the DG integrations. This is followed by EP technique with AEL of between RM200,000.00 and RM300,000.00 except for the Wind-Wind-Wind integration. The MALO technique shows inconsistent cost reduction by using Wind-Wind-Wind (yellow bar), PV-Diesel-Wind (light blue bar) and PV-PV-Wind (green bar) integrations, where the AEL values are higher than the condition without DG integration. The worst performance is shown by the LSF Analytical, where all types of DG integrations via this method failed to reduce the AEL below the scenario without DG integration.

From the cost analysis, the proposed LSF-

Figure 2: Minimum voltage magnitude by all methods – IEEE 69-bus system

Figure 3: Annual economic loss by all methods – IEEE 69-bus system

Figure 4: Annual cost saving by all methods – IEEE 69-bus system

MALO results in the highest cost saving of at least RM200,000.00 using most of the DG integrations, as illustrated in Figure 4. This is followed by the EP technique with ACS of at least RM100,000.00, excluding the Wind-Wind-Wind integration. As the AEL for LSF Analytical and MALO techniques reflect some inconsistencies, they have negative cost savings for most of the DG integrations, indicating a waste of cost.

Overall, the most effective DG integrations are PV-PV-PV, PV-Diesel-Wind, PV-PV-Diesel and PV-PV-Wind integrations. By using the LSF-MALO technique, these four types of DG integrations are able to provide a voltage magnitude above 0.95 p.u. with considerable cost savings of at least RM200,000.00. Even though the Diesel-Diesel-Diesel integration offers the highest cost saving of over RM300,000.00, it is a non-

renewable DG technology, which suffers from high greenhouse gas emissions.

The results of this study demonstrate that the LSF-MALO algorithm significantly outperforms other methods, such as MALO, EP, and LSF Analytical, in optimizing DG placement and sizing. LSF-MALO consistently reduced power losses (P_{loss}), improved voltage stability (V_{min}), and achieved the lowest annual economic loss (AEL) and substantial cost savings (ACS), particularly in configurations like PV-PV-PV and Diesel-Diesel-Diesel. These findings highlight the effectiveness of LSF-MALO in balancing both technical and economic objectives, making it a valuable tool for utilities seeking to optimize DG integration. Practically, adopting LSF-MALO can help power system operators reduce operational costs, improve grid stability, and enhance system performance,

especially as the demand for renewable energy integration increases. This approach can contribute to more cost-effective, reliable, and sustainable energy systems.

3.3 Multi-type DG Placement in IEEE 69-Bus System under Changing Loadings

In the previous sections, the performance of DG placement was evaluated at the base case condition, where the reactive loadings in the system were kept constant. Reactive power flow is crucial for maintaining overall system stability, ensuring proper voltage profiles, and minimizing power losses. Any uncontrolled consumption of reactive power by loads can significantly impact the distribution network, which might cause extreme voltage drop and high magnitude of power losses. Therefore, to observe the robustness of the proposed method, the multi-objective LSF-MALO algorithm is further tested under changing reactive loadings in the IEEE 69-bus system from the base case to 100% of maximum loading.

The graphical illustrations on minimum voltage magnitude (V_{min}), annual economic loss (AEL), and annual cost saving (ACS) under changing reactive loadings for the IEEE 69-bus system are shown in Figures 5 to 7. In the figures, only the top ten DG integrations that show the best performance, in terms of V_{min} , AEL and ACS, are included in the graphs.

Figure 5 presents the top ten V_{min} graphs using different methods and different types of DG integrations. As can be observed, all methods improve the magnitudes of V_{min} above the scenario without DG placement. The LSF Analytical approach dominates the top four DG integrations (PV-PV-Diesel, PV-Wind-Diesel, PV-PV-PV and PV-PV-Wind integrations), achieving a V_{min} close to 1.00 p.u. for all loading percentages, which is higher than the other methods. Following this, the proposed LSF-MALO technique with the same DG integrations as that of LSF Analytical maintains V_{min} above 0.95 p.u. for all loading percentages. In contrast, the MALO technique is the least effective, with V_{min} slightly below 0.95 p.u., while the EP technique is not in the top ten, indicating the worst performance of V_{min} .

Later, the top ten AEL graphs for all methods are shown in Figure 6. Most of the methods, with various types of DG integrations, successfully reduce the AEL below the scenario without DG placement (except for the MALO technique using PV-PV-PV integration). The proposed LSF-MALO

technique offers the lowest AEL of at most RM200,000.00 via four types of DG integrations (PV-PV-Diesel, PV-Wind-Diesel, PV-PV-Wind and PV-PV-PV), even under changing load conditions. The second-best performance after the proposed method is the EP technique, with an AEL of at most RM300,000.00 for the same types of DG integrations as the LSF-MALO; a rather considerable cost gap of RM100,000.00 compared to the one obtained by the LSF-MALO technique. The least effective method is the MALO technique since it results in a higher AEL of almost RM350,000.00 for PV-PV-Diesel integration, and the highest AEL of almost RM450,000.00 for PV-PV-PV integration. The LSF Analytical technique is not in the top ten of the AEL graphs, indicating the worst performance.

These findings result in the top four highest cost savings by the LSF-MALO technique, using four types of DG integrations (PV-PV-Diesel, PV-Wind-Diesel, PV-PV-Wind, and PV-PV-PV), as observed in Figure 7. By using those types of DG integrations, the proposed LSF-MALO technique offers the highest cost savings with ACS ranging between RM200,000.00 and RM250,000.00, while the rest of the methods yield ACS below RM150,000.00. LSF Analytical is not in the top ten of the ACS graphs, indicating the method failed to provide cost savings even after DG implementation.

The findings demonstrate that the LSF-MALO technique outperforms other methods, such as MALO, EP, and LSF Analytical, in optimizing DG placement under varying reactive loading conditions. Specifically, the LSF-MALO method consistently maintains a minimum voltage magnitude (V_{min}) above 0.95 p.u., even under maximum load conditions, ensuring grid stability. Additionally, the LSF-MALO technique provides the lowest annual economic loss (AEL) and highest cost savings (ACS) across multiple DG configurations, highlighting its robustness and effectiveness in real-world applications where load conditions are dynamic. These results suggest that utilities can rely on LSF-MALO for optimizing DG placement, ensuring both technical stability and economic efficiency, even in the face of fluctuating demands. The ability of LSF-MALO to deliver consistent performance under different load scenarios makes it a highly practical and reliable tool for modern power systems aiming to integrate distributed generation efficiently.

Top 10 Minimum voltage magnitude, V_{min} (p.u.) using different methods under multiple loadings: IEEE 69-bus

Figure 5: Minimum voltage magnitude under changing loadings by different methods – IEEE 69-bus system

Top 10 Annual Economic Loss, AEL (RM) using different methods & DG types under multiple loadings: IEEE 69-bus

Figure 6: Annual economic loss under changing loadings by different methods – IEEE 69-bus system

Top 10 Annual Cost Saving, ACS (RM) using different methods & DG types under multiple loadings: IEEE 69-bus

Figure 7: Annual cost saving under changing loadings by different methods – IEEE 69-bus system

4. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the performance of the Loss Sensitivity Factor-Mutated Ant Lion Optimizer (LSF-MALO) algorithm in optimizing the placement and sizing of Distributed Generation (DG) units in a power distribution network. The LSF-MALO algorithm's multi-objective framework successfully achieves a balance between three crucial objectives: minimizing real power losses, improving voltage magnitude, and reducing annual economic losses. The LSF-MALO algorithm's performance was validated using the IEEE 69-bus system under different loading situations and with other types of distributed generation (DG), such as photovoltaic (PV), diesel, and wind turbine units. The findings demonstrate that the LSF-MALO algorithm consistently surpasses other methods, including LSF Analytical, EP, and MALO, particularly in scenarios that involve combinations of PV-Diesel-Wind and PV-PV-Wind. These configurations resulted in substantial decreases in power losses and significant improvements in

voltage profiles, leading to significant annual cost savings. The study emphasizes the outstanding and reliable performance of the LSF-MALO algorithm in handling various DG integrations and loading circumstances. This contributes to it being a promising tool for improving the effectiveness and dependability of modern distribution systems.

5. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

While this study presents promising results, several limitations must be acknowledged. The analysis was conducted using the IEEE 69-bus system, which may not fully capture the complexities and scale of larger distribution networks. Future research should extend the proposed methodology to more extensive systems, incorporating realistic load profiles and generation scenarios. Furthermore, additional studies are needed to explore the real-time implementation of the LSF-MALO algorithm in operational power grids, considering dynamic load variations and the

integration of energy storage systems to reflect practical operational conditions better.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the Institute of Postgraduate Studies (IPSiS), Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia for the financial support of this research. This research is supported by IPSiS UiTM under the Journal Support Fund.

REFERENCES:

- [1] U. Department of Energy, "An Assessment Of Energy Technologies And Research Opportunities Chapter 3: Enabling Modernization of the Electric Power System," 2015.
- [2] *Distributed Generation in Liberalised Electricity Markets*. OECD, 2002. doi: 10.1787/9789264175976-en.
- [3] A. Shuaibu Hassan, S. Yanxia, and Z. and Wang, "Optimization techniques applied for optimal planning and integration of renewable energy sources based on distributed generation: Recent trends," *Cogent Eng*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 1766394, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1080/23311916.2020.1766394.
- [4] P. Paliwal, N. P. Patidar, and R. K. Nema, "Planning of grid integrated distributed generators: A review of technology, objectives and techniques," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 40, pp. 557–570, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.200.
- [5] S. A. Adegoke, Y. Sun, A. S. Adegoke, and D. Ojeniyi, "Optimal placement of distributed generation to minimize power loss and improve voltage stability," *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 21, p. e39298, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e39298>.
- [6] Z. Abdmouleh, A. Gastli, L. Ben-Brahim, M. Haouari, and N. A. Al-Emadi, "Review of optimization techniques applied for the integration of distributed generation from renewable energy sources," *Renew Energy*, vol. 113, pp. 266–280, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2017.05.087.
- [7] A. Rezaee Jordehi, "Allocation of distributed generation units in electric power systems: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 56, pp. 893–905, 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.11.086>.
- [8] K. E. Adetunji, I. W. Hofsajer, A. M. Abu-Mahfouz, and L. Cheng, "Category-Based Multiobjective Approach for Optimal Integration of Distributed Generation and Energy Storage Systems in Distribution Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 28237–28250, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3058746.
- [9] S. Nagaballi and V. S. Kale, "Pareto optimality and game theory approach for optimal deployment of DG in radial distribution system to improve techno-economic benefits," *Appl Soft Comput*, vol. 92, p. 106234, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106234>.
- [10] K. Surendra and C. Vyjayanthi, "Fault Level Analysis in Modern Electrical Distribution System Considering Various Distributed Generations," in *2018 International Conference on Power, Energy, Control and Transmission Systems (ICPECTS)*, 2018, pp. 36–42. doi: 10.1109/ICPECTS.2018.8521615.
- [11] A. A. S. M. Adnan *et al.*, "Optimal Distributed Generation For Loss Minimization Using Sand Cat Swarm Optimization," *J Theor Appl Inf Technol*, vol. 102, no. 7, pp. 3120–3130, 2024, [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85190588341&partnerID=40&md5=b2eb2ea8500aa582c9b7f2658138303d>
- [12] A. Abdullah, I. Musirin, M. M. Othman, S. R. A. Rahim, S. A. Shaaya, and A. V. Senthil Kumar, "Optimal Integration of Active and Reactive Power DGs in Distribution Network via a Novel Multi-Objective Intelligent Technique," in *2024 IEEE 4th International Conference in Power Engineering Applications: Powering the Future: Innovations for Sustainable Development, ICPEA 2024*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2024, pp. 157–162. doi: 10.1109/ICPEA60617.2024.10498595.
- [13] P. K. Saurav, J. Islam, P. Borah, S. Mansani, and P. Kayal, "Allocation and Performance Assessment of Dispatchable Distributed Generators with Multi-objective Planning Criteria," in *2023 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Smart Technologies for Power, Energy and Control, STPEC 2023*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2023. doi: 10.1109/STPEC59253.2023.10430599.
- [14] H. P. C, K. Subbaramaiah, and P. Sujatha, "Optimal DG unit placement in distribution networks by multi-objective whale optimization algorithm & its techno-economic

- analysis,” *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 214, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.epsr.2022.108869.
- [15] A. S. Hassan, Y. Sun, and Z. Wang, “Multi-objective for optimal placement and sizing DG units in reducing loss of power and enhancing voltage profile using BPSO-SLFA,” *Energy Reports*, vol. 6, pp. 1581–1589, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2020.06.013.
- [16] S. Kumar, K. K. Mandal, and N. Chakraborty, “Optimal DG placement by multi-objective opposition based chaotic differential evolution for techno-economic analysis,” *Applied Soft Computing Journal*, vol. 78, pp. 70–83, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.asoc.2019.02.013.
- [17] N. A. B. A. Rahman, Z. B. A. Hamid, I. B. Musirin, and N. A. B. Salim, “Hybrid Loss Sensitivity Factor And Mutated Ant Lion Optimizer For Optimal Distributed Generation Placement With Multiple Loadings,” *J Theor Appl Inf Technol*, vol. 101, no. 16, pp. 6703–6715, 2023, [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85173733093&partnerID=40&md5=009dbb881541089ad4c535e80ea0822f>
- [18] R. Rigo-Mariani and V. Vai, “An iterative linear DistFlow for dynamic optimization in distributed generation planning studies,” *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 138, p. 107936, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.107936>.
- [19] “PRICING & TARIFFS.” Accessed: Jun. 29, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tnb.com.my/residential/pricing-tariffs/>
- [20] “FiT Rates for Solar PV (Non-individual (> 500 kW)) (21 years from FiT Commencement Date).” Accessed: Jun. 29, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www3.seda.gov.my/iframe/>
- [21] A. Albani, M. Z. Ibrahim, C. M. I. C. Taib, and A. A. Azlina, “The optimal generation cost-based tariff rates for onshore wind energy in Malaysia,” *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 10, no. 8, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.3390/en10081114.
- [22] R. Zailan, S. Nurzalikha Zaini, M. Ikram Mohd Rashid, and A. Razak, “Techno-Economic Study for Hybrid Renewable Energy System for Coastal Residential Application in,” *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING TECHNOLOGY AND SCIENCES (IJETS)*, vol. ISSN, no. 1, pp. 2462–1269, 2018, doi: 10.15282/ijets.5.1.2018.1007.
- [23] S. G. Sasi Kumar, S. Sarat Kumar, and S. V. J. Kumar, “DG Placement Using Loss Sensitivity Factor Method for Loss Reduction and Reliability Improvement in Distribution System,” *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, vol. 7, pp. 236–240, 2018, [Online]. Available: www.sciencepubco.com/index.php/IJET
- [24] S. Mirjalili, “The ant lion optimizer,” *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 83, pp. 80–98, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.advengsoft.2015.01.010.
- [25] N. A. A. Rahman and T. K. A. Rahman, “Improved Cuckoo Search for Loss Allocation in Transmission Line.,” *Esteem*, vol. 13, no. June, pp. 55–65, 2017, [Online]. Available: <http://ezproxy.auckland.ac.nz/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=aph&AN=123938997&site=ehost-live&scope=site>